

REBOOT
EUROPEAN FILM COMPETITIVENESS

Report on survey from FAMES

Project: Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT

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PROJECT SUMMARY

The **REBOOT** project aims to leverage existing strengths, identify and address weaknesses, and strategically plan for enhanced competitiveness in the areas of policy, practice, and audience engagement. Specifically, the project seeks to explore the longstanding assets and critical gaps in European competitiveness and its related policies. This includes developing methods to effectively *measure, analyze, and evaluate* the impact of these policies and the strategic pathways they create.

In parallel, the project focuses on preparing for the future by examining audience preferences and behaviors, as well as evolving modes of film content production. These elements are crucial, as today's youth will shape and engage with the European audiovisual landscape in the coming decades as creators, consumers, and leaders in both industry and policy. The consortium therefore adopts a forward-looking approach, examining not only the present ("what is") but also the past ("what has been") and future ("what will be") through innovative perspectives.

REBOOT's ambition is to provide a full set of knowledge of the European film industry, which maximises its existing strengths, combined with strategic and tactical dimensions of action for the optimisation of the potential held in European youth publics, understood both as emerging audiences and as citizens. Specifically, the ambition of the project combines several dimensions, which reinforce each other but are listed separately for analytical purposes (and in no particular order): a) increasing support for young people's engagement with European film; b) strengthening the place of the EU in the global audiovisual economy, particularly in light of the rise of video on demand (VOD); c) supporting cultural diversity in the EU film industry; d) addressing the need for a different understanding of competitiveness and relevant indicators in this context; and e) recognising and supporting the importance for the EU of film and, more broadly, of the cultural and creative sector as a geopolitical asset.

REBOOT's ambition is to generate a comprehensive body of knowledge about the European film industry, aiming to maximize its current strengths while delivering actionable strategies to optimize its potential among Europe's youth—both as emerging audiences and as active citizens.

The project's ambition is multifaceted and includes several interrelated objectives, each critical for achieving sustainable competitiveness:

1. **Enhancing young people's engagement with European film**, fostering a deeper connection with the cultural richness of European audiovisual works.
2. **Strengthening the EU's position in the global audiovisual economy**, particularly in response to the rapid expansion of Video-on-Demand (VOD) platforms.
3. **Promoting cultural diversity within the EU film industry**, ensuring representation and the preservation of Europe's unique cultural identity.
4. **Reconceptualizing competitiveness**, by developing new indicators and frameworks that better reflect the dynamics of the European film ecosystem.
5. **Recognizing the strategic value of the film industry and the broader cultural and creative sectors** as critical geopolitical assets for the EU.

By addressing these objectives, the REBOOT project aligns with the priorities of Horizon Europe, fostering innovation, inclusion, and competitiveness in the European audiovisual sector.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE REPORT

This report delves into future trends aimed at enhancing the competitiveness of the European Film Industry (EFI) by addressing three key dimensions: creativity, skills development, and production practices. It aspires to lay the foundation for a sustainable and globally competitive future for the industry, one that embraces innovation and cultural diversity as cornerstones of its success.

A central focus of the report is the exploration of the role of music as an innovative force within film production, emphasizing its cultural and educational dimensions. Despite its critical importance, this area remains under-researched and under-utilized, yet it holds significant potential to enhance the artistic appeal, emotional depth, and overall quality of film productions. Music's integration into the filmmaking process not only elevates the viewing experience but also contributes to the broader cultural ecosystem, shaping the industry's identity and impact.

To address these opportunities, the study undertakes a comprehensive comparative analysis of the creative production processes for film music. Its primary objective is to provide an in-depth account of the steps involved in composing music for visual media, supported by practical case studies that illustrate real-world applications. Throughout the analysis, the report highlights strategies employed by composers to optimize production timelines and costs while maintaining exceptional aesthetic quality. These insights are intended to offer replicable methodologies that can bolster the competitiveness and efficiency of future film music productions.

The report also features a detailed case study examining the recording sessions of an orchestra, offering concrete examples of best practices and innovative approaches within the domain of film music production. This case study draws upon the experiences of FAMES, a renowned international music orchestra and partner in the Europe Creative project (CREA-CULT-2021-PECE). The inclusion of FAMES ensures a distinctly European perspective, demonstrating the integration of excellence in music recording with collaborative practices that exemplify innovation and resourcefulness in the industry.

By analyzing and showcasing these processes and strategies, this report contributes to a growing body of knowledge and practical tools aimed at strengthening the EFI's creative and competitive edge. It seeks to inspire stakeholders across the audiovisual sector to embrace music as both a cultural asset and a driver of innovation, ultimately reinforcing the position of European film on the global stage.

1 INTRODUCTION

Music and Film analysis: A brief introduction

Recent reports from the Society for European Composers and Songwriter Alliance highlight the need to address the situation of audiovisual composers, considering the nature of their contracts and the emerging challenges posed by AI in music creation. Music is now fully embedded in the film industry's production process, encompassing various phases: initial drafts and conceptualization with the director and production team, commissioning, deliverables, editing, and mixing.

Competitiveness in this context is influenced not only by costs but also by the time required to deliver an appropriate draft of the music. Simultaneously, as an integral part of audiovisual media, composed music serves as both an economic and cultural product (see Rostam Neuwirth, in Ward, 2008). The music production workflow embodies these dimensions, incorporating cultural and individual choices alongside qualitative content that may or may not translate into economic value. For this reason, analyzing this workflow—i.e., the creative process—has become essential to understanding and improving the dynamics of film music production.

The workflow of music composition for media has become increasingly complex, as Steven Saltzman highlights in *Music Editing for Film and Television* (2017), where he details the critical phases of this process. This complexity arises from the diverse skills and multiple stages involved. Whether in mixing, post-production, or music creation itself, composers rely heavily on digital tools, with the Digital Audio Workstation (DAW) being a cornerstone of their work.

This raises several questions: Which software is most commonly used? Which plugins are preferred, and for what specific outcomes? Do certain plugins dominate particular phases of the creative process? Additionally, to what extent are the sounds produced inherently linked to these digital tools, whether as foundational elements or within production workflows? It is worth noting that composers are not always responsible for the mixing phase, often delegating this task. Regardless, delivery typically follows the mixing phase in the form of a stem file containing all the separate music tracks.

Finally, the economic context of music composition is another crucial factor to consider. Film and audiovisual projects demand significant investment across all production areas, and music is no exception. Economic constraints often influence whether composers can record with real instrumentalists or must rely on virtual instruments, which, in turn, affects the creative process—a topic explored in greater depth in the final section of this report. Another fundamental economic aspect for creators is compensation, whether through royalties or alternative forms of remuneration, which remains a key consideration for the sustainability of their work.

The scientific literature on film music can be broadly categorized into a few main areas: the history of film music¹, the analysis of film music² (possibly by genre), composition guides³. However, there is a notable lack of research linking film music to the industrial context of its creation⁴. A few exceptions exist, such as Solenn Hellégouarch's 2020 study on the creative process in music and film. However, this work focuses on well-known composer-director duos, which represent specific cases characterized by unique and highly specialized working conditions.

This report addresses this gap through a dual focus: first, by analyzing and deconstructing the creative process behind a film score, including the influence of various constraints; and second, by exploring how this process is integrated into the broader production environment of the film industry.

2 DATA AND METHODS

This study focuses on a comparative analysis of the creative production processes in film music, based on interviews with a panel of 19 individuals. The panel includes 10 professionals—one of whom is a senior composer based in Los Angeles, with music recently featured in the international Amazon Prime series *Kali*, ranked No. 1 in France and No. 2 in Brazil and 9 students.

The professionals were engaged through a survey conducted in collaboration with the FAMES orchestra. The study aims to shed light on the film music production chain (from original idea to mix), identifying key processes and challenges involved in achieving competitiveness in the field.

2.1 Qualitative Data

The interviews were conducted primarily via teleconferencing tools such as Zoom, although some were held face-to-face. The questionnaire comprised eight main themes, covering topics such as the composers' musical careers, the stages of composing music for film (or other media)—from receiving a script or image to delivering the final composition—and budget considerations (refer to the questionnaire for details). For example, the question “*Can you tell me about your studies?*” provided insight into the academic backgrounds of the composers, most of whom had studied at conservatories or undertaken specialized training in music for screen at various institutions. More technical questions, such as “*Which Digital Audio Workstation (DAW) do you use*

¹ For example : Mervyn Cooke (2008). *A History of Film Music*. Cambridge University Press; James Wierzbicki (2009). *Film Music : A History*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis.

² Emilio Audissino (2017). *Film/Music Analysis. A Film Studies Approach*. Palgrave MacMillan; Kathryn Kalinak (2010). *Film Music : A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford University Press; Mathew J. Bartkowiak (2009). *Sounds of The Future. Essays On Music in Science Fiction Film*, MacFarland.

³ Lalo Schiffrin (2011). *Music Composition For Film and Television*. Berklee Press Publication; Sonny Kompanek (2010). *From Score to Screen. Sequencers, Scores, & Second Thoughts. The New Film Scoring Process*. Schirmer Trade Books.

⁴ Jeff Smith(2014). “ ‘The Tunes They Are A-Changing’: Moments of Historical Rupture and REconfiguration in The Production and Commerce of Music in Film”, in David Neumeyer (dir.) *The Oxford Handbook of Film Music Studies*, chapter 10 (270-290), Oxford University Press.

most often? Is the software ever imposed on you?", revealed personal and industry habits within this profession.

The interviews were transcribed and systematically summarized into tables, particularly focusing on each composer's production workflow. These tables highlighted detailed similarities and differences across the participants. A team of three researchers collaboratively managed this part of the project, including designing and testing the questionnaire, conducting the interviews, transcribing the responses, and processing the qualitative data into comparative tables.

For instance, among the composers surveyed, 16 identified their first step as engaging with the project (e.g., analyzing scripts, images, animatics, or initial edits), with five explicitly including discussions with the director (4 professionals and 1 student). For 12 participants, this engagement occurred later in their process (11 as the second step, 1 as the third step), while 1 participant did not consider this step relevant.

Another notable aspect was the recording phase, which varied significantly among composers. For 9 participants (7 students and 2 professionals), recording was identified as a distinct step. For the remaining 11, it was integrated into the broader process of score production. Among those who treated recording as a separate phase, 3 described it as optional and highly dependent on the budget, while 1 noted that recordings were done at home. Those who did not differentiate between recording and score production often relied solely on scoring software (e.g., Dorico or Sibelius), with 6 of them focusing exclusively on digital tools, and 1 participant delegating the recording process altogether.

Regarding remuneration, insights from 7 professional composers revealed varied approaches. Two depended on agency representation, two relied on production companies, two prepared quotes, and one used a standardized rate sheet. Interestingly, half of the surveyed composers ultimately worked under "buyout" contracts—one-time payment agreements where the composer forfeits rights to the distribution of their work.

2.2 Problems encountered and Solutions

The development of the questionnaire was the initial task, but it proved to be a complex endeavor. The stages of the creative process in film music differ significantly from those typically associated with classical music. Kinderman (2012) illustrates how, in the context of composing iconic musical works from the 19th and 20th centuries, composers invested considerable time in constructing harmonic meanings based on abstract emotions. They often refined chords to enhance effects of surprise or tension and made adjustments to written scores to enrich poetic expressions. Similarly,

in studies compiled by Dave Collins (2012), Bailes and Bishop demonstrated how improvisation can enhance the immediacy of musical creation. However, while these foundational stages—musical imagination, initial ideas, and emotional connection with sound—are well-established, addressing the more pragmatic aspects of editing and realization posed a distinct challenge. As Saltzman (2017) notes, these stages involve complex technical iterations with software and production tools – that could potentially limit creative freedom.

To address this complexity, the initial questionnaire was developed using empirical data informed by experiences in genetic criticism (Trubert & Donin, 2010; Trubert, 2017). The challenge was to adapt these insights to the specific context of film music composition. This required several rounds of collaboration between Noémie Auizerate, who was tasked with conducting the interviews, and the scientific team, comprising Julie Mansion-Vaquié and Jean-François Trubert. Their goal was to design a questionnaire that effectively captured the full spectrum of composition stages and processes.

As is often the case in qualitative surveys, the first iteration of the questionnaire fell short of expectations. It failed to provide sufficient depth or detail regarding the stages of soundtrack production. To refine the model, the team used interviews with experienced film composers and their associated questionnaires as benchmarks. This iterative approach allowed for a broader and more targeted range of questions, better aligned with the nuances of the creative process. It also facilitated a deeper understanding of the differences in workflow and the varying levels of importance composers assigned to each stage of production.

3 THE ORCHESTRA AND THE CONTEXT OF CASE STUDY

In the case of the FAMES symphonic orchestra, it is notable that, due to economic constraints, some composers choose not to pursue original recordings. This decision is particularly regrettable for two main reasons. First, recording with real instruments often delivers a much richer emotional impact, providing significant added value to the soundtrack. Second, in an era dominated by advances in artificial intelligence, the use of live orchestras, such as FAMES, introduces an incomparable and authentic quality that digital tools alone cannot replicate.

Nevertheless, the question of competitiveness in today's cultural industries transcends purely economic or logistical considerations. It also involves qualitative and aesthetic dimensions, which are becoming increasingly critical, especially in light of the challenges and opportunities presented by AI technologies. Ensuring the continued use and accessibility of live orchestras like FAMES will be vital for maintaining both artistic integrity and the industry's cultural value.

3.1 What is FAME and the Survey Conducted

Established in 2007, **FAME'S Project** ([FAME'S Institute](#)) is a prominent production company specializing in orchestral music recording for the film industry. Over the past 15 years, FAME'S has played a transformative role in the global orchestral recording sector, cultivating an extensive international network of composers and production companies. To date, the company has produced over 4,000 orchestral projects, catering to markets across Europe, the United States, South America, India, and Asia.

Building on its vast expertise, FAME'S actively supports emerging European classical musicians while engaging with diverse audiences. In response to increasing demand, the company inaugurated a 2,000 m² orchestral studio in Skopje, Republic of North Macedonia, in 2017. This state-of-the-art facility, designed in collaboration with French acoustic engineers and Macedonian architects, is equipped with exceptional acoustics and advanced technical capabilities, making it a premier destination for orchestral music recording.

In 2022, FAME'S launched the **European Creative Orchestral Program for Skilled Youth**, under the framework of the first Pan-European Cultural Entities Program. Co-funded by FAME'S Project, the European Union (Creative Europe), and the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of North Macedonia, this initiative aims to nurture the artistic and professional development of talented young European classical musicians. By offering innovative training approaches, professionalization opportunities, and cutting-edge performance experiences, the program seeks to empower the next generation of orchestral talent within a uniquely creative framework

3.2 Survey

A survey was conducted to evaluate the attractiveness and competitiveness of the recording process offered by the FAMES orchestra in Macedonia. This case was compared to the Cannes National Orchestra, with which the University of Côte d'Azur has an established agreement as part of its Master's program in Music Composition for Film and Sound Design.

While the most straightforward indicator of competitiveness might be the cost of recording, which is significantly lower at FAMES than in France, this metric alone is neither decisive nor entirely objective. To accurately assess competitiveness, costs must also be indexed against parameters such as the cost of living and regional economic conditions. Furthermore, the European Commission has historically sought to facilitate interoperability within the audiovisual sector, promoting the cross-border distribution of goods and services (see Anna Harbor, 2008 in Ward).

A more relevant measure of competitiveness is the range and quality of services that FAMES provides in addition to its orchestral recording capabilities. These supplementary services and workflows significantly enhance its appeal compared to other options. While we are unable to disclose pricing details due to confidentiality, we can outline the components that make FAMES competitive.

The first key feature is that FAMES offers an all-inclusive orchestral recording service. It operates a dedicated studio specifically designed for music production for visual media, equipped with permanently installed microphones connected to a recording booth. This setup allows for immediate use without extensive preparation.

Deliverables include individually recorded tracks for each instrument, organized either by moment or instrumentation, totaling over 48 independent audio files. This flexibility enables composers to create their own mix starting from a comprehensive guide track.

Secondly, the sessions are conducted remotely, eliminating the need for the composer to travel to Macedonia. FAMES uses two integrated systems: Zoom for direct communication with the conductor to request specific retakes, and Audiomovers for high-fidelity playback of the orchestra's performance. Furthermore, each musician is equipped with individual headphones synchronized to a click track, enabling precise timing and facilitating the resumption or correction of specific passages with minimal effort.

These technical and operational advantages—what could be termed a "pre-recording" phase—streamline the production process significantly. Composers receive a recorded and potentially edited deliverable within just two hours.

For comparison, sessions with the Cannes National Orchestra as part of the Master of Science in Film Music and Sound Design are notably more time-intensive. Without a dedicated recording room, the Cannes National Orchestra requires at least four hours to prepare a 60-microphone setup and an additional four hours to dismantle it after the session. Equipment rentals and deliveries also add logistical complexity. In contrast, FAMES's ready-to-use setup saves more than eight hours while delivering comparable results. While the Cannes National Orchestra may offer undeniable sound value, the competitive advantage of FAMES lies in its efficiency. This time savings can have a substantial impact on production schedules and the final output.

The broader implication is clear: similar efficiency gains could be realized in other regions if more dedicated recording studios with ready-to-use technology were available. The competitiveness of music production for audiovisual content increasingly depends on the ability to provide such facilities, enabling high-quality orchestras to perform recordings within short or even ultra-short workflows.

3.3 Composition processes

Figure 1 illustrates how Laetitia Pansanel Garric, a film music composer, conceptualizes the process from the initial phase (1) to the final delivery to production (8). At the outset, the initial phase of communication with the director and production team is paramount. This stage involves understanding the tone, atmosphere of the film, and the main characters. Ms. Pansanel also advocates for creative freedom whenever possible, enabling her to fully explore her artistic vision. One notable strategy she employs is making immediate counter-proposals with significant contrasts—for example, using dense, frenzied chords for a chase scene. This approach helps clarify the production team's vision early on, allowing for more precise refinements later.

In the second phase, upon receiving the film's images, she conducts a breakdown to structure each moment of the film. This leads into the research phase (3), where she explores specific tonal colors, selects instruments with the desired character, and, if necessary, begins preliminary recordings.

Phase (4) involves improvising live to the images without interruption, a technique that allows her to expand her bank of creative ideas. In phase (5), she revisits the production team to gather feedback, which informs the final modifications to the composition.

From here, she edits the music into a score, creating a simulated mix for the musicians that includes a tempo track. She then initiates the recording session, after which the music is mixed and edited in a Digital Audio Workstation (DAW) before final delivery to the production team.

Figure 1 : Composition process of Laetitia Pansanel Garric

Figure 2: Composition process of Julien Vega

Figure 2 provides a comparative perspective by illustrating the process used by another composer, Julien Vega. It becomes immediately clear that Vega's workflow differs significantly from that of Ms. Pansanel.

Notably, the first two stages are distinct: in Vega's process, the initial step (1) involves receiving images—this was stage (2) for Ms. Pansanel—followed by a discussion phase with the production director. This dialogue focuses particularly on defining the desired atmospheres, often using existing music catalogues as reference points.

Phase (3) holds particular importance in Vega's process. At this stage, he composes a one-minute piece of music using high-quality virtual instruments. This composition demonstrates the emotional connection to the images, often achieved through improvisation, and establishes harmonic sequences designed to evoke specific emotions and create a memorable emotional identity for the film.

In phase (4), Vega reconnects with the production management team to gather feedback. Phase (5) then involves initial adjustments to align the composition more closely with the visual elements, progressing toward a deliverable. If needed, phase (6) includes the realization of an orchestral score, followed by a final mix in phase (7), which completes the process.

4 CONCLUSION

The findings of this report underscore that the competitiveness of the European film music sector hinges on a nuanced understanding of the creative process, coupled with the optimization of technical and human resources (see also Boris Furduj (2019) who explores how modern composers utilize digital sequencing and sample-based virtual instrument). By analysing workflows, economic constraints, and technological innovations—such as those exemplified by the FAMES orchestra—this study demonstrates that the future of Europe’s audiovisual industry lies in better alignment between creativity, production efficiency, and strategic planning.

To enhance competitiveness across the European Film Industry, several key recommendations emerge:

1. **Targeted Investments:** The establishment of dedicated orchestral recording studios equipped with advanced technologies can significantly reduce production timelines and enhance workflows. Ellis-Geiger (2007) discusses how purpose-built recording environments and technological integration streamline the film scoring process, leading to increased efficiency and higher-quality outputs (but outside Europe, nevertheless the Value chain is the same).
2. **Support for Cultural Diversity:** Increasing funding for original film music is crucial for promoting cultural diversity within the European film industry. The European Parliament's report on cultural diversity and the conditions for authors in the European music streaming market (Iban Garcia Del Blanco, 2024) emphasizes the importance of supporting diverse musical expressions to enrich the cultural landscape and ensure a variety of content is available to audiences.
3. **Education and Innovation:** Expanding training opportunities for composers in advanced technological contexts, including the integration of artificial intelligence and digital tools, is essential.
4. **Adaptation of EU Policies:** Developing specific indicators to assess the impact of European audiovisual policies on music production is vital : public funding influences movie success, suggesting that tailored policies can enhance both economic performance and cultural value in the film industry (Weber, Merchant, Kunz, 2024).

Additionally, while the role of artificial intelligence in creative workflows remains nascent, its potential to accelerate certain phases of music production is promising. However, further research is required

to evaluate its impact on artistic quality and employment within the sector. This report aspires to provide European policymakers, industry professionals, and stakeholders with actionable insights and practical tools to drive forward an audiovisual industry that is not only globally competitive but also rooted in Europe's cultural and creative values.

5 ANNEX - QUESTIONNAIRE FOR COMPOSERS

Exploratory questions :

Can you tell me about your studies?

Describe your most recent activity as a film music composer?

What kind of media do you prefer to compose for (video games, films, series, documentaries, cartoons, etc.)?

Do you have any film genres for which you prefer to compose? Why?

Describe the steps you follow to produce a film music composition?

How do you organise your production time? Do you work a little every day or do you do large work sessions less often?

What do you like most about being a composer? What do you like least?

What do you think have been the greatest technological advances in composition? In your opinion, has technology helped or hindered composition?

1, Composition script

In what form is the script communicated to you?

(Can you suggest any changes to the script?)

Which scenes do you think are the hardest to accompany musically?

What information do you look for when discussing the script with the director / What are the main questions you ask to understand the director's vision?

What specific elements of the film do you look for to guide your composition, such as key sequences, action moments, important dialogue, etc.?

How do you work with the director to refine and adjust the way the music reinforces the film's emotions?

Do you have any specific techniques or methods for translating emotions into musical choices, such as instrumentation, tempo, harmony, etc.?

How do you use compositional techniques, such as leitmotiv or thematic development, to reinforce emotions throughout the film?

What approaches do you take to avoid falling into musical stereotypes linked to emotions, while remaining faithful to the director's vision?

2, Musical idea, idea research phase

During your last composition, do you remember when the first idea arrived?

Do you look for themes for each character or a main theme before you start working on each scene?

Do you compose before or after seeing the images? Which is easier for you?

Do you attend film shoots for inspiration?

Are you sometimes inspired by composers or compositions to create a film score? And which ones?

3, First designs, mock-ups:

On average, how many first mock-ups do you make before you find the right one?

How do you start your 1st mock-up?

Do you visualise the scenes to help you make your first sketches?

What guides your choice of melody, harmony and instrumentation for the main theme?

How do you approach composing a film's main theme?

Do you compose only instrumentally, only with a computer, or both? How do you choose between the 2? Which composition method are you most comfortable with?

4, Production back and forth

In general, do you have a good relationship with the programming team?

Has production ever refused to make any changes?

On average, how many return visits are there with production before an agreement is reached? How do you deal with requests for changes or revisions to the music that could affect the initial budget?

5, Mixing (return trips?) to Scoring to digital recording Do you still have to go back and forth with production after the first mix?

What are the biggest problems you encounter during recording?

What is the largest number of people you have recorded? For which project?

What software do you use for scoring?

Do you often use technical assistance for digital recordings?

6, Post-prod

What are the biggest changes you make in post-production?

Do you often use DAWs?

Which DAW do you use most often? Is the software ever forced on you?

What plug-in do you use most often?

If you compose on DAW, how do you choose your sounds? What do you remove most often from your work?

In what order do you use your plug-ins?

7, Delivery

Does the production team ever not like the composition you hand in and have to change it after delivery?

How long can a film music production take from script visualisation to delivery of the composition?

Which project did you prefer to work on and why?

8, Budget

What factors do you take into account when estimating the budget for a musical composition?

How do you negotiate fees and royalties with directors or production studios?

Do you have specific criteria for determining your rates according to the size of the project, the reputation of the director, the overall budget for the film, etc.?

Have you ever been faced with major budget constraints when creating music for a film? How did you manage to overcome them?

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